

Zeros of Clebsch-Gordan coefficients or $3j$ symbols using the Labarthe patterns

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Abstract

The linear zeros of $3j$ coefficients can be deduced from parametrized solutions of a Diophantine equation. In the present note, we point out that the L -patterns, introduced by Labarthe, are a powerful tool of angular-momentum theory. In order to illustrate their efficiency, we apply the corresponding formalism to the determination of the Diophantine equation from which the weight-1 non-trivial zeros of $3j$ symbols or Clebsch-Gordan coefficients can be deduced.

1 Introduction

In quantum mechanics, Clebsch-Gordan coefficients describe how individual angular-momentum states may be coupled to yield the total angular-momentum state of a system. In the literature, Clebsch-Gordan coefficients are sometimes also known as Wigner coefficients or vector coupling coefficients. They are closely related to Wigner's $3j$ symbol [1] by

$$C_{a\alpha, b\beta}^{c(-\gamma)} = (-1)^{a-b-\gamma} \sqrt{2c+1} \begin{pmatrix} a & b & c \\ \alpha & \beta & \gamma \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $C_{a\alpha, b\beta}^{c\gamma}$ is the Clebsch-Gordan coefficient and

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b & c \\ \alpha & \beta & \gamma \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

the $3j$ symbol for angular momenta a , b and c with respective projections α , β and γ .

For the $3j$ coefficients of $SU(2)$, there exists a class of zeros which are called non-trivial or structural zeros, as opposed to trivial zeros due to a symmetry or a violation of one or

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more triangle relation. Zeros of $3j$ coefficients find many applications in atomic and nuclear physics [2–4]. There is also a more fundamental mathematical motivation, since the non-trivial zeros of $3j$ coefficients correspond to roots of Hahn polynomials [5]. This is the reason why they are often called “polynomial zeros”. Moreover, non-trivial zeros have appeared in relation to exceptional Lie groups and algebra [1, 6].

In a systematic approach, the non-trivial zeros of $3j$ coefficients can be classified by the minimum length of the single-sum expression for the coefficients. This minimum length corresponds to the number of terms when the coefficient is rearranged as a generalized hypergeometric series [7]. The number of terms in this sum minus one is called the degree or the weight of the coefficient [8]. Subsequently, zeros of strictly positive degree are by definition non-trivial zeros [9]. The zeros of degree 1 of the $3j$ coefficient are quite easy to find, and explicit expression for them, not taking into account the Regge symmetries, have been provided by Varshalovich [10].

A long time ago, Labarthe introduced the decomposition of coupling-recoupling $3nj$ coefficients ($3j$, $6j$, $9j$, $12j$, etc.) in terms of closed diagrams [11], in a paper entitled “Generating functions for the coupling-recoupling coefficients of $SU(2)$ ”. Based on the Bargmann formalism [12] and graphical calculations, the results are expressed in terms of sums over two finite sets only of subgraphs of the Jucys graph of the coefficient [13]. It allows one to obtain a formula of the same form as Racah’s $3j$ and $6j$ formulas for any coupling-recoupling coefficient. The latter approach is very powerful, but has not been properly valued, probably because the above quoted original 1975 paper was written in a rather complicated way for physicists. The so-called L -patterns were used, by Labarthe himself, in two successive papers [14, 15] about hidden angular momenta, providing a better insight into the way the machinery proceeds. A few authors, however, recognized the potentialities of the L -patterns (see for instance Refs. [16, 17]).

Beyond the derivation of expressions of the $3nj$ coefficients, Labarthe used the formalism to present a complete parametrization of the linear zeros of the $6j$ coefficient [18].

In this note, we apply the same technique to show that the Diophantine equation for the linear zeros of $3j$ coefficients can also be easily obtained using the L -patterns. Beyond this specific simple result, our aim is above all to draw attention to this formalism, which is likely to yield new results in angular momentum theory.

2 The Labarthe patterns

The $3j$ symbol can be expressed in terms of so-called “Labarthe patterns” (or L -patterns) [11, 16–18]. The primitive L -patterns are

$$\begin{aligned}
 e_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix}, & e_2 &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \\
 e_3 &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix}, & e_4 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \\
 e_5 &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 & -\frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix}, & e_6 &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

They satisfy the linear dependency relation

$$e_1 + e_2 + e_3 = e_4 + e_5 + e_6 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

The Labarthe pattern associated to the $3j$ symbol (2) can be expressed as a linear combination of primitive L -patterns according to

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b & c \\ \alpha & \beta & \gamma \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{\lambda=1}^6 n_{\lambda} e_{\lambda}, \quad (5)$$

yielding the Labarthe formula for the $3j$ symbol:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b & c \\ \alpha & \beta & \gamma \end{pmatrix} = Q \sum_{n_1} \sum_{n_2} \cdots \sum_{n_6} \frac{(-1)^p}{n_1! n_2! \cdots n_6!}, \quad (6)$$

with

$$p = \sum_{i=1}^3 n_i \quad (7)$$

and where the normalization factor Q is given by

$$Q = \frac{1}{\sqrt{T_{abc} T_{abc, \alpha\beta\gamma}^- T_{abc, \alpha\beta\gamma}^+}}, \quad (8)$$

with

$$T_{abc} = \frac{(a+b+c+1)!}{(b+c-a)!(c+a-b)!(a+b-c)!} \quad (9)$$

and

$$T_{abc, \alpha\beta\gamma}^- = \frac{1}{(a-\alpha)!(b-\beta)!(c-\gamma)!} \quad (10)$$

as well as

$$T_{abc, \alpha\beta\gamma}^+ = \frac{1}{(a+\alpha)!(b+\beta)!(c+\gamma)!}. \quad (11)$$

We obtain a set of six linear equations on the n_k 's:

$$\begin{aligned} n_1 &= a + b - c - n_5 \\ n_2 &= b + \beta - n_5 \\ n_3 &= a - \alpha - n_5 \\ n_4 &= c - b + \alpha + n_5 \\ n_6 &= c - a - \beta + n_5. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

which are equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned} a &= \frac{1}{2}(n_2 + n_3 + n_5 + n_6) \\ b &= \frac{1}{2}(n_1 + n_3 + n_4 + n_6) \\ c &= \frac{1}{2}(n_1 + n_2 + n_4 + n_5) \\ \alpha &= \frac{1}{2}(n_2 - n_3 - n_5 + n_6) \\ \beta &= \frac{1}{2}(-n_1 + n_3 + n_4 - n_6) \\ \gamma &= \frac{1}{2}(n_1 - n_2 - n_4 + n_5). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Therefore, in such a way, the six-index sum is reduced to a single sum and the summation over n_5 must be restricted by the conditions $\max(a - c + \beta, b - c - \alpha) \leq n_5$ and $n_5 \leq \min(a + b - c, b + \beta, a - \alpha)$, which enables one to recover the Racah expression

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} a & b & c \\ \alpha & \beta & \gamma \end{pmatrix} &= \frac{1}{Q} \sum_{n_5} \frac{(-1)^{a-b-\gamma+n_5}}{n_5!(a+b-c-n_5)!} \\ &\quad \frac{1}{(b+\beta-n_5)!(a-\alpha-n_5)!} \\ &\quad \times \frac{1}{(c-b+\alpha+n_5)!} \frac{1}{(c-a-\beta+n_5)!}. \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

3 Linear zeros of $3j$ coefficients

The (necessary and sufficient) condition for a non-trivial weight-1 zero of a $3j$ coefficient can be derived directly from the explicit alternating sum expression for the respective coefficient as described in detail in Ref. [9]. Because of the symmetries of these coefficients, the conditions for a zero can be stated in various equivalent ways. Weight-1 zero means that at least one 1 occurs as an element of the Regge [19] or Bargmann [12] symbols. The following Regge symbol

$$\left\| \begin{array}{ccc} 1 & x+u-1 & y+v-1 \\ u+v-1 & x & y \\ x+y-1 & u & v \end{array} \right\| \tag{15}$$

is equal to the $3j$ coefficient

$$\begin{pmatrix} (x+u)/2 & (y+v)/2 & (x+y+u+v-2)/2 \\ (x-u)/2 & (y-v)/2 & (-x-y+u+v)/2 \end{pmatrix}. \tag{16}$$

In order to find the polynomial zeros of a $3j$ coefficient, we are looking for the sextuplets $\{n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4, n_5, n_6\}$ such as

$$\begin{bmatrix} (x+u)/2 & (y+v)/2 & (x+y+u+v-2)/2 \\ (x-u)/2 & (y-v)/2 & (-x-y+u+v)/2 \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{\lambda=1}^6 n_\lambda e_\lambda. \tag{17}$$

We find the decomposition

$$ve_1 + xe_2 + e_3 + (y-1)e_4 + (u-1)e_5 \tag{18}$$

and using $e_3 = e_4 + e_5 + e_6 - e_1 - e_2$ (see Eq. (4)), we get

$$(v-1)e_1 + (x-1)e_2 + ye_4 + ue_5, \tag{19}$$

and applying

$$\sum_{n_1} \sum_{n_2} \cdots \sum_{n_6} \frac{(-1)^p}{n_1!n_2! \cdots n_6!} = 0 \tag{20}$$

with

$$n = \sum_{\lambda=1}^6 n_{\lambda}, \quad (21)$$

we obtain the Diophantine equation

$$vx = uy, \quad (22)$$

which is equivalent to

$$(x + u)(y - v) = (x - u)(y + v). \quad (23)$$

Using that representation, the zeros of $3j$ coefficients can be parametrized¹.

4 Conclusion

We presented an illustration of the L -patterns for the coupling-recoupling $3nj$ coefficients. The formalism was applied by Labarthe for the determination of the zeros of $6j$ coefficients. In this note, it was shown that the parametrization of the weight-1 linear zeros of $3j$ coefficients can be easily obtained from the L -patterns. Beyond such a simple application, our goal is to shed light on that outstanding theoretical tool, and to stimulate the discovery of new properties and relations. We plan to apply the L -patterns to the determination of the non-trivial zeros of $9j$ symbols.

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¹In Refs. [16, 17], the authors have a factor $(n + 1)!$ in the numerator of the argument of the sum in Eq. (6). Such a factor was included in the normalization coefficient by Labarthe. Both expressions are actually equivalent.

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